
SUMMARY: In this section, I present a definition of life that does not contradict the natural sciences but sets a new benchmark. I add brief philosophical reflections and observe that life is a function of the mind, which is a potential whole. I conclude that life should be defined according to its observable purpose, and then it would be a Self-articulated-composition-of-the-Unity, where unity is a totality of possibilities.

The definition of life should start with identifying the common attributes of all living beings. We should then question whether we observe all the traits of living beings and whether there are traits that we cannot observe or understand. To define life precisely and informatively, we need to create a definition that reflects our scientific knowledge of the vital phenomenon. There are numerous definitions of life formulated from different characteristics of living beings, such as replication, metabolism, evolution, energy, autopoiesis, etc. Often, definitions of life are biased by the research focus of the person making the definition. Since any definition of life must connect with what we observe in nature, our strategy should be to identify measurable attributes or characteristics of organisms, which are called traits. Trait-based approaches have been widely used in systematics and evolutionary studies.

The search results support the idea that the definition of life should start with identifying the common attributes of all living beings and that there are numerous definitions of life formulated from different characteristics of living beings. The results also suggest that trait-based approaches have been widely used in systematics and evolutionary studies.

Life is usually in the form of a list of characteristics that apply to organisms, their parts, their interactions, or their adaptation. ¹ Finding fundamental organizing principles is the current intellectual front end of systems biology. ²

According to Benner ³, any definition of life is intricately connected to a theory that gives it meaning and there are various definitions of life held in the astrobiology community by considering their connected "theories of life." These include a popular definition that holds that life is a "self-sustaining chemical system capable of Darwinian evolution" following a suggestion by Carl Sagan, at a NASA committee (1994).

We should start with a list of the main observable characteristics of life. Thus Hillis David noted in *Principles of Life* ^{4,42} that, the overwhelming evidence for the common ancestry of life lies in the many distinctive characteristics that are shared by all living organisms, and all organisms:

- are composed of a common set of chemical components such as nucleic acids and amino acids, and similar structures such as cells enclosed within plasma membranes
- contain genetic information that uses a nearly universal code to specify the assembly of proteins
- convert molecules obtained from their environment into new bio-logical molecules
- extract energy from the environment and use it to do biological work
- regulate their internal environment
- replicate their genetic information in the same manner when repro- ducing themselves
- share sequence similarities among a fundamental set of genes
- evolve through gradual changes in their genetic information.

But now we are getting the point, how many components are needed for a basic life form, let's say for a minimally functional cell? According to Moger-Reischer ⁵, the cell is the simplest independent functional unit of life. However, even unicellular model organisms that are touted for their tractability are complex, possessing thousands of genes and proteins, many of which remain uncharacterized even after decades of in-depth investigation. Possessing only essential genes, a minimal cell can reveal mechanisms and processes that are critical for the persistence and stability of life. The complexity of a genome is reflected by the number of genes that it contains, a quantity that varies by orders of magnitude across the tree of life. Whereas some obligately endosymbiotic bacteria have fewer than 200 protein-coding genes, many plant and animal genomes contain more than 20,000 genes. In principle, the simplest organism is one that possesses only the minimum number of genes for survival and reproduction in a given environment. Any mutation in such an organism could lethally disrupt one or more cellular functions, placing constraints on evolution, as revealed by the fact that essential proteins change more slowly than those encoded by dispensable genes. Furthermore, organisms with streamlined genomes have fewer targets on which positive selection can act, therefore limiting opportunities for adaptation ^{id}.

The cell is the simplest independent functional unit of life, but a cell is already an extremely complex organism and we need to go even deeper and deeper. So, if we could map

and understand every single molecular process in a cell, we would have a better grasp of the fundamental principles of life ⁶.

At this point, we can turn our attention to the evolution of microbial parasites. Taking into account David Nicholson et. Al ⁷, this evolution involves the counterplay between natural selection forcing parasites to improve and genetic drifts forcing parasites to lose genes and accumulate deleterious mutations. Here, the authors tell us that for to understand how this counterplay occurs at the scale of individual macromolecules, it is necessary to describe cryo-EM structure of ribosomes from *Encephalitozoon cuniculi*, a eukaryote with one of the smallest genomes in nature. Then, the extreme rRNA reduction in *E. cuniculi* ribosomes is accompanied with unparalleled structural changes, such as the evolution of previously unknown molten rRNA linkers and bulgeless rRNA. Furthermore, *E. cuniculi* ribosomes withstand the loss of rRNA and protein segments by evolving an ability to use small molecules as structural mimics of degenerated rRNA and protein segments. The authors show that the molecular structures long viewed as reduced, degenerated, and suffering from debilitating mutations possess an array of compensatory mechanisms that allow them to remain active despite the extreme molecular reduction ^{id}.

Considering the imaginable extreme, it is possible that an array of compensatory mechanisms is added to an initial matter to generate life. This array could constitute a predetermined permanence, one so-called matrix, on various levels of complexity, and could be transmitted by a teleportation-like mechanism ^{8,9,10,11}, but this is far from our subject. In addition to the observable characteristics of life, it is a personal observation that the transmitter of this matrix must also possess the general attributes of Omnipresence and Omnipotence. As we see below, a living agent should possess these attributes, or seek to possess them.

Here we can also mention the neutral theory of evolution ¹² which has become central to the study of evolution at the molecular level, in part because it provides a way to make strong predictions that can be tested against actual data. The neutral theory holds that most variation at the molecular level does not affect fitness and, therefore, the evolutionary fate of genetic variation is best explained by stochastic processes. This theory also presents a framework for ongoing exploration of two areas of research: biased gene conversion, and the impact of effective population size on the effective neutrality of genetic variants. A stochastic process is connected with random probability but this is just another perspective, not a very wise one and especially not one that is easy to explain mathematically. Perhaps this is why it

is generally accepted, as it offers only the prospect of a possible mystery, but not necessarily a logical or useful one.

In the search for general characteristics of life, it is important to mention some widely accepted stages in the origin of life. It is suggested that primitive forms of life must have had the same primary evolutionary mechanism as more advanced ones. Therefore, the more primitive forms of life would allow for an easier observation of the mechanism of evolution and, consequently, the observation of the characteristics of life.

A broad array of origin of life (OOL) models are described in the current literature, and many of them use the same general framework and are governed by common precepts, remarks Kathryn Lanier and Loren Williams in *The Origin of Life: Models and Data*¹³. The authors note that, Molecular Toolbox is a common set of molecular components that is fixed over time and is surprisingly restricted in composition, and Universal Gene Set of life, is a set of genes shared as orthologs throughout the tree of life, and found in essentially every living system, to be important and useful data. And then, there is no evidence that Darwinian processes can revise the Molecular Toolbox or radically alter the Universal Gene Set.

Going to the origin, for Orgel¹⁴ it is widely believed that biology based on DNA, RNA, and proteins was preceded by the biology of an "RNA world" in which enzymes were composed of RNA alone. And then, the origin of RNA replication is thus the central puzzle of the origins of life.

Koonin Eugene in *Comparative genomics, minimal gene-sets and the last universal common ancestor*¹⁵ claims that comparative genomics, using computational and experimental methods, enables the identification of a minimal set of genes that is necessary and sufficient for sustaining a functional cell. Therefore for most essential cellular functions, two or more unrelated or distantly related proteins have evolved; only about 60 proteins, primarily those involved in translation, are common to all cellular life. The reconstruction of ancestral life-forms is based on the principle of evolutionary parsimony, but the size and composition of the reconstructed ancestral gene-repertoires depend on relative rates of gene loss and horizontal gene-transfer. The present estimate suggests a simple last universal common ancestor (LUCA) with only 500–600 genes^{id}.

The last universal common ancestor of known life is called LUCA, and the L in the name is important because it was not the first organism, but the last before the bifurcation that led to all modern organisms. Cornish-Bowden Athel and Cárdenas María Luz in *Life before LUCA*¹⁶ have observed that the last universal common ancestor of all living organisms (LUCA) already had the capacity to code for many proteins, and had some of the same

bioenergetic capacities as modern organisms. Therefore an organism at the origin of life must have been vastly simpler, and authors invite the question of how to define a living organism and forces the definition of LUCA to be revised. But LUCA is an imagined organism and already it seems extremely complex, so we return to the idea that there is an array of compensatory mechanisms that allow molecular structures to remain active despite the extreme molecular reduction caused by mutations.

In summarizing the researchers' observations, it was concluded that chemical reaction automata are not designed to explain how life originated, but rather to understand better how a basic metabolism functions. They are a representation of the living world without reproductive and adaptive capacities ^{17,195}.

In the search for general characteristics of life, it is worth mentioning that Plutarch posed the question of the chicken or the egg causality dilemma as a philosophical matter in his essay "The Symposiacs" in the 1st century CE. This dilemma raises the question of which came first: an array of compensatory mechanisms or life itself. If the array of compensatory mechanisms allows molecular structures to remain active and maintain life, then it exists before life. On the other hand, if life appeared first, it would establish the compensatory mechanisms. Alternatively, it could be considered that the compensatory mechanisms themselves are a basic form of life, but in this case, there would be a rule that has no maintaining agent. The question of which came first, the array of compensatory mechanisms or life, is left unanswered, but the dilemma is formulated for consideration.

Understanding how brains evolved is critical to determine the origin of centralized nervous systems, and brains are patterned and there is evidence to suggest that brains are homologous¹⁸. Nowadays, despite the many advances in neurobiology, physiology, developmental and cell biology on this matter, unraveling the evolutionary history of the nervous system is still contentious, according to José M. Martín-Durán, Andreas Hejnl ¹⁹.

In partial conclusion, it appears that at the end of biology lies a set of information that is indecipherable to the observer but seems to be interconnected and presumably so, given the observable results. Now, as I will note later, there is a collection of data that can be referred to as "Mental" and is also indecipherable to a third-party observer. The interconnected information set underlying biology may be indecipherable, but by observing its characteristics, a simulation can be devised that is limited but useful.

If we were to make observations, the best results seem to be obtained not so much by observing the exact physical mechanism of functioning as by observing the metaphysical rationality of functioning. Here, it seems necessary to make some observations from

philosophical approaches to the subject of the world as mental. When we formulate the term mental, we refer to a whole world arranged in the mind, not a certain, but a universal. Therefore, we should observe the reactions to store it under certain circumstances and not try to copy it. Even for an identical copy, we are not certain that we will possess the key to turn it on, and this key is hidden behind the individual mental construct. It is indecipherable to another.

There is a vast philosophical work that discusses ontological aspects, but I detail what I find interesting from a phenomenological perspective, starting and stopping at Martin Heidegger from *Being And Time* ²⁰. I then tried to establish from here some principles that I prepared, to be implemented somehow in computer code.

The philosopher said that to begin with you have to approximate superficially what life is. First, it has been maintained that 'Being' is the 'most universal' concept. It has been maintained secondly that the concept of 'Being' is indefinable. Thirdly, it is held that 'Being' is of all concepts the one that is self-evident and Being is always the Being of an entity ^{20.29}. The philosopher highlights the term "Dasein", which is purely an expression of its Being ^{20.33}. Interpreting all entities within-the-world, however, we have always 'presupposed' the world, and even if we join them together, we still do not get anything like the 'world' as their sum. The philosopher then wonders whether, if we start with the Being of these entities, is there any avenue that will lead us to exhibiting the phenomenon of the world ^{20.101-102}. Among the usual things Dasein can lose itself in what it encounters within the world ^{20.106-107}.

Dasein is the principle of being, as the direction of formation and movement of mental entities, because it giving way, as taking a direction, belongs essentially to Dasein's Being-in-the-world. When an entity within-the-world has already been proximally freed for its Being, that Being is its "involvement" ^{20.110}. The philosopher notes that it is urgent to work out the 'formal' idea of worldhood, the idea of a phenomenon modifiable ^{20.113}.

This modifiable phenomenon, manifests itself exclusively immanently, the rest is naturalness, food for the senses. Worldhood as a modifiable phenomenon only manifests itself in the perfect tense. Therefore when we speak of having already let something be involved, so that it has been freed for that involvement, we are using a perfect tense a priori which characterizes the kind of Being belonging to Dasein itself ^{20.117}.

Therefore the computer code that aims at simulating this worldhood, imagination of the natural world, must pursue this perfect tense a priori which according to the philosopher belongs to Dasein itself. Here is the tense of the verb which I call "continuu". As the

philosopher says, Dasein, in its ontical dealings with the entity thus encountered, can thereby let it be involved in the ontical sense^{20,117}.

Returning to the earliest forms of life and the perspective of defining life, life can be defined as the capacity of the living agent to usefully optimize another agent with which it enters into a contract, without necessarily seeking to alter it. The compound living agent will have another agent in contact, another useful optimization, etc. The living agent and the optimized agent useful to the living agent constitute a first universality, which is relative to the living agent. Universality is also optimized by the inclusion of new agents. Life should be defined according to the observable purpose, and then it would be a self-articulated composition of the unity, where unity is observed as a totality of possibilities.

As we have seen before, molecular structures possess an array of compensatory mechanisms that allow them to remain active despite the extreme molecular reduction. This first mechanism is Dasein as the principle of being, which would support the designation of the mental.

The further up the evolutionary ladder a biological entity goes, the higher its mental processing capacity. Thus, starting from the other end of observable evolution, although the nature of human uniqueness in brain evolution is generally accepted, there are also anatomical-functional cross-species comparisons of frontal areas that remain controversial. To provide a novel interpretation of the evolution of primate brains, sulcal morphological variability of the medial frontal cortex was assessed in Old World monkeys (macaque/baboon) and Hominoidea (chimpanzee/human). The authors of a study²¹ show that both Hominoidea possess a paracingulate sulcus, which was previously thought to be unique to the human brain and linked to higher cognitive functions, such as mentalizing. Also, they show systematic sulcal morphological organization of the medial frontal cortex that can be traced from Old World monkeys to Hominoidea species, demonstrating an evolutionarily conserved organizational principle²¹.

This principle is also observed by the researcher Koyabu *et al.* in the article Mammalian skull heterochrony reveals modular evolution and a link between cranial development and brain size²². These studies reveal that the multiple skeletal components of the skull originate asynchronously and their developmental schedule varies across amniotes. They present us that ossification timing of the neurocranium was considerably accelerated during the origin of mammals and cranial heterochrony in mammals has occurred in concert with encephalization but within a conserved modular organization.

Evolution is based on an outline that develops under certain circumstances, resulting from the possibility of observing the progress of common structures. This progress does not necessarily come at the expense of other biological entities but rather with the acceptance of preserving biodiversity. Relevant experiences are memorized, and the entire useful world is preserved in the mental.

Results of a study demonstrated that trait inferences were used to derive mental state inferences, and that the accuracy of trait estimates predicted the accuracy of mental state inferences. Findings are in accordance with the Mind-space theory, that representation of the Target mind is used in the inference of their mental states ²³.

Looking through a narrow window, learning unpleasant things and remembering them is advantageous for the organism for avoiding future recurrences, and memories that are irrelevant to survival or adaptation tend to fade away either by graceful degradation ²⁴. Observable biological organisms evolve, and even within the same species, increasing body and brain size constitutes a key macro-evolutionary pattern, for example, in the hominin lineage. The mechanisms behind these changes possibly include environmental, demographic, social, dietary, and technological factors ²⁵.

The head direction system functions as the brain's internal compass anchored to local environmental cues. Computational models of the HD network suggest that plasticity mediates the integration of visual information within the network ²⁶. Important to remember that experience may shape brain structure ²⁷.

The extensive lines of bidirectional communication between the brain and visceral organs facilitate integration of internally arising interoceptive cues that are critical for survival ²⁸. Mental processes and their neural substrates are intimately linked to the homeostatic control of internal bodily state. There are a set of distinct interoceptive pathways that directly and indirectly influence brain functions. The anatomical organization of these pathways and the psychological/behavioral expressions of their influence appear along discrete, evolutionarily conserved dimensions that are tractable to a mechanistic understanding ²⁹.

The whole visible development of the biological body raises the standards of the neurological system, which includes not only the brain but also any other neural structures. These neural structures create a so-called own world, serving as relevant memory ready for immediate action. As the brain evolves, it incorporates its own world of perceived

experiences, which later become transmissible through cultural patterns and form relevant behavioral patterns. Moving forward, life is a function of mind, and mind is a whole. However, it is important to consider the current functional limitations of the biological support, such as limitations of action, fatigue, and decay, in order to accurately assess neural functionality in creating representations of uniformly repeated facts and facts that occur between things.

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NOTE: When I wrote the exponent 17.195, I was referring to paper no. 17 in the bibliography page 195, and when I wrote the exponent 31.39,3/1367 I was referring to paper no. 31 in the bibliography and percentage out of total for eBook.